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English Pronunciation Patterns among Educated Yoruba Female Pastors in Nigeria: A Model for Standard English Stress Assignment

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Abstract

The spoken English in Nigeria exhibits features that are explicitly distinctive, and thus, a cynosure for linguistic investigation. This paper examined the extent to which selected educated Nigerian female Yoruba Pastors approximate standard English patterns, with the aim of evaluating their suitability as pronunciation models for Nigerian speakers. Prince and Liberman's (1977) Metrical Phonology served as the theoretical insight for the study. Three female Educated Yoruba pastors were purposively selected Their messages were downloaded from YouTube and transcribed. A total of 18 words and 18 utterances, 6 from each Pastor, were randomly extracted and a Acoustic analysis was done using Praat. The findings revealed that the selected educated female Yoruba pastors exhibited patterns of stress assignment in their pronunciation of words and in connected speech. They assigned stress in their words and utterances. The metrical analysis showed that the stressed syllables in the words were perceived to be more prominent than all other syllables, irrespective of their location in the utterances. The study found stress assignment of the pastors suitable as a model for Nigerian English.

Keywords: Pronunciation modeling, educated female Yoruba pastors, approximation, Standard British Stress

Introduction

Studies in linguistics have been able to establish the fact that English language, a second language in Nigeria, has proven to be challenging to the Nigerian learners and general users. Crystal notes that in these countries, the English language functions "as the primary medium of instruction and communication, in such domain as government and politics, the law court, broadcasting and the educational system, religious settings etcetera". The status and the spread of the English language in the world have become remarkably high yet, the language still seems to be difficult for a lot of Nigerians.

Of all the aspects, spoken English has been the most problematic for non-native speakers. Nigerian users of English Language attain better international intelligibility and conformity with Standard English in writing than in speaking. Also, with little or no exposure of most Nigerians to the L1 environment, the problem associated with spoken English among Nigerian users may continue; and it may result in a wider range of the mesolectal and basilectal categories of Nigerian English

Previous researchers such as Adesanya (2014), Toki (2014), Adeniyi (2006), Aina (2018), Agboyinu (2018), Gbadegesin (2021) and Akande (2022) have shown that Nigerian speakers of the English language have challenges in the aspect of spoken English, as a result of lack of exposure to the language in its native or original form or setting. Hence, researches have been in search for ancillary models. There is the need for a native-like model to assist learners and general users of English attain international intelligibility, considering the roles that the language plays in the world as a global language. Since earlier models have been insufficient and deficient, language use of some educated female pastors could be investigated, to affirm their suitability as models for the teaching and learning of stress assignments to Nigerian users of English.

Since most learners of English in Nigeria lack the exposure to English in the first language setting. There have been continued quest for a particular variety of English which can serve as a model for learners and general users of English as a second language in Nigeria. Such a variety

is expected to be near standard British English (no study has said everyone must sound exactly like a native speaker). Several suggestions have been made by scholars who believe that native-like accent should be adopted since standard Nigerian English may be difficult to achieve due to the influence of the Nigerian variation

The need for better models of English pronunciation has resulted in studies that recommend some non-enculturation sources as access to Standard English pronunciation. This is due to the fact that English language has become the most important language in the world today, and its position has been compared with that of Latin in medieval times' (Banjo, 1996).

According to a social learning theorist, Bandura, he opines that individuals may learn appropriate behavior observing others. To him, leaders may influence their follower's ethical behavior through modeling. To him, learning process and social behavior which proposes the new behavior can be acquired by observing and imitating others. Subsequent upon this, Carter investigated that many Nigerian church members often imitate the way of speaking their pastors. Hence, considering the fact that religion has had a lot of influence on Nigerians and the great number of followership that some educated Nigerian pastors record, this study therefore attempts to find out whether or not the selected female educated pastors could serve as another source of modeling and thus assume a model of standard British Stress Assignment for Nigerian learners and general English Language users.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

1. investigate how well these selected educated female pastors approximate Standard English word stress assignment;
2. find out if they are able to reduce vowels in their utterances;
3. confirm that the use of emphatic stress in the sermons of the selected educated female Yoruba pastors do not hinder communication; and
4. appraise the suitability of selected educated female Yoruba pastors as models for Standard English sentence stress

Literature Review

Nigeria has been said to be a highly religious country considering the large numbers of churches (Ogidi, 1997; Ikeazota, 2013; Kitause and Achunike, 2013; Okai, 2016). According to Ogidi (1997: 11), ‘Nigeria is a country with the largest number of churches per capital in the world’. With the expansive media presence of Nigerian pastors especially the selected participants for this study, followership has been extended greatly beyond the live congregation. With the aid of technology, many sermons by Nigerian pastors are now available on CDs, MP3, MP4 formats while many are also accessible on YouTube and websites of most religious organizations.

Many Nigerian church members often imitate the way of speaking of their pastors. Carter (2009: 190) refers to such influence by church leaders on followers as ‘Referent Power’. According to Carter, ‘it is the power that comes from the attractiveness of the leader and follower’s desires to be like the leader’. Referent power can also be said to be the ability of a leader to influence a follower because of the follower’s admiration, respect, or identification with the leader. Referent power is a form of reverence gained by a leader who has strong personal skills on something. Referent power becomes important particularly as organizational leadership becomes increasingly about collaboration and influence and less about command and control. In a formal setting, referent power is most easily seen in the charismatic leader who excels in making others feel comfortable in his or her presence.

Similarly, Bandura (1977) ‘social learning theory, suggests that individuals learn appropriate behavior by observing others actions and their consequences. Bandura proposes that leaders may influence follower’s ethical behavior through modeling. Social learning theory is a theory of learning process and social behaviour which proposes that new behaviour can be acquired by observing and imitating others. In addition to the observation of behavior, learning also occurs through the observation of rewards and punishment, a process known as *vicarious reinforcement*. Social Learning Theory emphasizes the importance of observing, modeling, and imitating the behaviors, attitudes and emotional reactions of others. Social Learning Theory considers how

both environmental and cognitive factors interact to influence human learning behavior.

Thus, in terms of social learning theory, the leaders serve as role models whose way or pattern of life is imitated by their followers (Badura, 1977; Brown, et al., 2005). This study focuses on the possibility of role modeling influence of some selected female Yoruba pastors on their followers in the assignment of stress.

Research in Modeling and Pronunciation of English in Nigeria

A pronunciation model is a carefully selected and defined accent of a language (Roach and Hartman, 1997). When we mention English language, the option of a model is either American English or British English simply because these two varieties have historical, social and political importance. Therefore, the two traditionally recognized pronunciation models of English are Received Pronunciation (RP) and General American (GA). RP is an accepted accent of social prestige that cannot be traced to any geographical area within England while General American (GA), the American standard model, covers a variety of American accents (Dunstan, 1969).

Awonusi, Ademola-Adeoye and Adedeji (2015:58) opines that the accent associated with the –‘upper ruling class is what came to be known as Received Pronunciation; (‘received’ in the sense of accepted pronunciation) or RP for short’.

Roach and Hartman (2007: v) claims that Jones describes the model he presents in the 1917 edition of his pronouncing dictionary as ‘Public School Pronunciation (PSP)’ which is ‘that most usually heard in everyday speech in the families of Southern English persons whose men folk have been educated at the great public boarding schools’. These authors explained further that Jones abandoned the term PSP in favour of RP in the 1926 edition. However, Roach and Hartman, as editors of the 2007 edition of the dictionary, state that they have ‘abandoned the archaic name Received Pronunciation’ for BBC English in that edition. They declare that the pronunciation model in the dictionary is that of ‘professional speakers employed by the BBC...as well as many commercial broadcasting organizations...’

Review of Empirical Studies on Pronunciation Modelling

Considering the present confusing state of RP, the challenge of appropriate English modeling for non-native speakers remains unresolved. Akinjobi (2008), it is stated in *Cambridge Encyclopedia of the English Language* that less than 3% of the people in Britain speak RP in a pure form, which has led to the acceptance to the claim that it is obsolete. Though RP is the target, it is not used in Nigerian classrooms in the practical sense because most Nigerian teachers, who have lived all their lives in Nigeria with no contact with native English, cannot pronounce the sounds appropriately and the pronouncing dictionaries (in book forms) only display the transcription of the words; so the students struggle with getting the transcription interpreted as well as getting the correct pronunciation of the words (Akinjobi, 2008).

The pursuit for a practical model for non-native learners has created inconclusive arguments among English linguists. Akande, (2022) describe that the recent growth in the use of English as an International Language (EIL) has given onto changes in learners' pronunciation needs and goals, and that the acquisition of a native-like accent and the potential to communicate with native speakers are no longer the paramount objective of the majority of learners. To her, what the learners need above all is to be able to communicate successfully with other non-native speakers of English from different L1 backgrounds. She, therefore, recommends a "radical rethink" in terms of the role of pronunciation and its aims within the curriculum, especially with English fast becoming the world's lingua franca.

Hence, efforts have been made by some scholars (Akinjobi, 2011; Aina, 2014; Toki, 2014, Adeniyi, 2016) to provide supportive models to aid Nigeria learners and users of English in general to achieve better pronunciation. Such models are expected to approximate to Standard British English. Models of English pronunciation are necessary considering the fact that the Received Pronunciation itself has been adjudged to be obsolete even in England as the BBC, which is the acclaimed foremost model of Standard British English.

Akinjobi (2011) examined the performance of postgraduate students of English at the University of Ibadan in assigning intonation tunes. Chomsky's linguistic competence and performance modified as

academic competence and linguistic performance in non-native setting was adopted as the theoretical model. The findings showed that academic attainments/competence does not necessarily guarantee linguistic performance in English pronunciation. By inference, the selected post graduate students are not suitable as models.

Adesanya (2014) investigated the degree to which Yoruba teachers of English language (YELTs) can be attested as models for assignment and reassignment of phrasal stress. She adopted Liberman and Prince's (1977) Metrical Theory and Akinjobi's (2011) concept, Academic Competence and Linguistic Performance, a modification of Chomsky's (1965) 'Linguistic Competence and Linguistic Performance'. Bandura's (1986) Social Cognitive Theory, which establishes that humans learn through modeling, serves as the ancillary framework for her study. She concluded that Nigerian English language teachers in Ogun and Lagos States were not able to correctly assign and reassign phrasal stress; hence, they are not suitable as models.

Also, Aina (2014) studied some English language teachers in Ogun state with the aim to find out their suitability as models for Standard British English stress assignment. 100 public and private school teachers, fifty, from each state were used. The participant performance was accessed with acoustic tools and in simple percentage. The findings revealed that the selected teachers of English language did not achieve appropriate stress assignment; hence, they are not suitable as models.

Adeniyi (2016) examined the approximation of educated elite Nollywood actors and actresses to Standard English stress assignment with a view to testing their acceptability as models for pronunciation among Nigeria speakers of English language. The author randomly selected 26 Nollywood films produced between 2000 and 2013 with a total of 157 scenes featuring 171 actors who played professional roles. The finding showed that Nollywood actors and actresses who have played the roles of educated elite approximate to SBE and thus suitable as supportive models for Nigerian speakers of English. However, sorting out which character to listen to or which ones not to listen to become cumbersome for learners.

In another study, Agboyinu (2018) examined the application of phonological rules (P-Rules) by selected Ogun State Senior Secondary

School teachers of English language (OSSSTEL) with a view to determining their degree of approximation to Standard British English (SBE). This was to determine whether or not they could be models for learners and the general users of English. Chomsky and Halle's generative phonology served as the framework for his study in which forty university graduate teachers of English were purposively selected from public and private secondary schools in each of the three Ogun State senatorial districts. Agboyinu found out that OSSSTEL did not apply English phonological rules appropriately as they deviated significantly in vowel reduction, liaison, morphophonemic alternation, cluster reduction, nasal assimilation rules.

Given the role- modeling influence of female Christian leaders in Nigeria – a nation widely recognized for its religious commitment -this study seeks to evaluate the suitability of selected educated Yoruba female pastors as models for standard British English stress assignment.

Theoretical framework

Metrical Phonology Theory is adopted in this study to represent stress based on the view of rhythm proposed by Liberman (1975) and later developed into a theory by Liberman and Prince (1977).

Methodology

The study adopted a mixture of purposive and random sampling techniques for participant selection and data collection. The study purposively selected Nigerian female pastors who are Yoruba, speak Yoruba as first language (L1), are university graduates of any discipline, are residents in the south western part of Nigeria have large audience and have international recognition. Among the several female pastors that meet these requirements, three were randomly selected for the study. The selected female pastors were: Funke Adetuberu of Faith Chapel International, Ibadan, Oyo State; Tope Ogunnoiki of Graceville Chapel, Ikeja, Lagos State; and Adenike Adeyemi, Day Star Christian Center, Oregun, Lagos. Three sermons of each of these female educated Yoruba pastors were randomly selected for the study. Also, 18 expressions and 18 words extracted out of context were randomly selected from each sermon and were run on PRAAT for acoustic

analysis. The records of the selected sermons of the three sampled educated female Yoruba pastors were downloaded from the YouTube. They were saved on an audio-visual device and converted to Mp3, on which they were played repeatedly.

Data Presentation and Discussion

Participant I extract 1

In this selected utterance of Participant I, two content words which are *flame* and *fire* were identified. The frequency of the pitch *flame* is 249.6Hz and *fire*, 115.3Hz. Ordinarily, *fire*, which is the last stressed syllable, is supposed to bear the nuclear stress. However, as evident in the hertz of each of the stressed syllables, the nuclear stress has been reassigned to *flame* which bears the emphatic stress as displayed in the spectrogram below:

Fig 1 Participant1 extract 2:

In the selected utterance of *Participant1*, only two content words were seen; *you*, produced with 414Hz and *still*, produced with 326.4Hz noticeable. Below is the spectrogram showing the pitch frequency in the extracted utterance.

Fig 2: Stressed syllable in the utterance of participant 1 extract 2.

The acoustic representations in Figure 2 above show the utterance of Participant I. The use of emphatic stress on the word *you* results in a shift of the nuclear stress from the first lexical word *are* to the next word *you* which bears the emphatic stress. The cumulative feature of stress is also confirmed in the utterance as *you* was produced with 415.8Hz against *are* which was 319.6Hz. Thus, the emphatic stressed word is *you* which have a higher frequency than *are*. Hence the emphasis is on *you* to mean a particular co-interact ants, the second person involved in the discourse. Not a third person. Note, the utterance was only selected randomly; hence the meaning might be subjective.

Participant1 extract 3

Three content words are noticeable in the selected utterance of Participant I extract 3. The words such as: *eagle* has 376.9Hz, *pow(er)ful* 270.6Hz, and *hun(ter)* 221.2Hz. This result also corroborates the cumulative feature of stress that each word or phrase has a single strongest stress (Roach, 1991; Hayes, 1992). The speech is analysed in the acoustic Figures below:

Figure 3:

The Figure above is the acoustic representation of the utterance of Participant I extract3. Ordinarily, *hunter* which is the last content word should take the nuclear stress, but the emphatic stress on *eagle* makes it assume the unclearly stressed syllable. It is also acoustically evident that the word eagle is the only word with the highest pitch prominence with 376Hz. By implication, the eagle, not an ostrich, not the dove nor a bat is a powerful hunter but the *eagle*. This explanation is based on the researchers intuition as the reason for the focus on *eagle* was not established because the utterance was only selected in the context of use.

Participant1 extract 4

Three content words are identified in the utterance of Participant I extract4. The utterance is analyzed below to show the pitch height of the stressed word in the utterance.

Fig 4 everything he touches is blessed

Figure.4 above shows the utterance of Participant I extract 4. highlighted in the spectrogram above is *everything* produced with the highest frequency of 412.9Hz. Ordinarily, the syllable *blessed* should have borne the nuclear stress, but a longer duration and a higher pitch was identified in the production of *everything*, which was meant to emphasize the preacher's message that it is *everything* a child of God touches that shall be blessed. The preacher's message is in the word *everything*. Not a fraction, not a certain percentage of what a child of god touches shall be blessed but *everything*. The word, *everything* was produced with 412.9Hz while *blessed* was produced with 334Hz.

Participant 1 extract 5

This particular utterance of participant1 extract5 has 6 content words with *said* produced with 346.8Hz, *path* with 269.9Hz, *just* 264Hz, *shine*, 255.2Hz, *brighter*, 292.7Hz, *brighter* 200.7Hz. The utterance is analyzed below to show both the pitch height of every syllable in the utterance. With the utterance of the participant here, she relayed the person whose path shall shine brighter.

Fig 5 Showing participant 1 in extract 5

Figure5 above shows the acoustic representation of the utterance of participant1 extract5. In the spectrogram above, *said* is seen highlighted has the stressed word. With obvious pitch height and highest hertz the

highlighted word has been stressed. The implication of this is that the lord has said it. He Lord didn't propose it nor suggest neither did he imply that *the path of the just shall shine brighter and brighter*. He said it. As we all know, Christ the Lord God honors his words more than his name. Once he has said it, it shall come to pass. Hence, he has said it; the path of the just shall shine brighter and brighter.

Participant 1 extract 6

In this selected utterance of participant 1 extract 6 two content words are identified in the utterance.

Fig. 6 showing 'get' as the stressed syllable

Figure 6 above shows the utterance of participant1 extract 6. From the spectrogram above, it's obvious that *get* has the highest pitch and produced with the most frequency hertz. *Get* is produced with 385.3Hz.

Participant 2 extract 1

Four content words are noticeable in the selected utterance of Participant 2 extract 1. The content words are: *family* has 270.3Hz, *let* 285.5Hz, *see* 241.9Hz and *hand* 191.1Hz. Highlighted in the spectrogram below is *who* produced with 387.5Hz. The speech is analysed in the acoustic Figures below:

Fig 7 showing who has the stressed syllable

Finding shows that the participants have been examined not to reduce vowels. In the analysis of the content words taken out of context show that the selected educated Yoruba pastors used full and strong vowels in unstressed syllable positions where the reduced vowel /schwa/ and /I/ are expected. This confirms the findings reached by Akinjobi (2004) who examined vowel weakening and unstressed syllable obscuration in educated Yoruba English. This work also establishes that the selected Yoruba female pastors do not reduce vowel.

Also, Finding shows that the participants have been examined to use sentence stress for emphasis as against the general claim by some scholars like Eka (1985) and Jowitt(2000) that sentence stress is rarely used for emphasis in Nigerian English. The stressed syllables were perceived louder than all other syllables in the sentence. This is as a

result of the fact that loudness is one of the cues to stress in any stress language, Standard British English inclusive. This study has been able to establish that the selected female educated Yoruba pastors make use of emphatic stress in their utterances. Regardless of the position of such syllable in the utterance (beginning, middle or end), regardless of whether or not it is a content word or a function word, for as long as it is foregrounded for emphasis by the speaker, it received the stress. This is evidently proven by the images from the spectrogram. One can see variation in the pitch of the participants with the highest pitch contour having the highest frequency. Hence, the stressed syllable in the utterance.

In all the randomly selected words and sentences of the selected female educated Yoruba pastors, all the syllables with emphatic stress have higher pitch than all other surrounding syllables as explained in the analysis. Hence, the selected female educated Yoruba pastors approximate to standard British English stress assignment and can serve as models for Nigerian learners of English and the general users.

Conclusion

In conclusion, all the stressed syllables, and words with emphatic stress have higher pitch than all other syllables as shown in the analysis. Hence, the selected Female Educated Yoruba Pastors approximate appropriately to Standard British English stress assignment and can serve as ancillary models for learners and general users of English in Nigeria. However, they are not ancillary models in the aspect of vowel reduction.

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